

The Influence of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of research is the risk of financing. Sources of data collection come from searches of national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus through the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the effect of BVS using a bibliometric study with the VOSviewer algorithm software; and (2) mapping the effect of BVS using a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The results showed that based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study, research on the influence of BVS was divided into 4 clusters and 74 topic items. Meanwhile, based on a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 4 influences of BVS on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implications and contributions of this research are to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Book Value per Share (BVS); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

Along with the development of increasingly sophisticated technology and information, the use of the Book Value per Share (BVS) ratio in the banking industry continues to grow. Many investors and analysts use this ratio to determine the value of bank shares and estimate potential future investment profits. This especially happens during fluctuating and volatile market conditions like today. However, the use of the BVS ratio in the banking industry is still a controversial topic. Some analysts argue that this ratio does not provide an accurate picture of a bank's performance because it does not take into account factors such as asset quality, management performance and growth prospects. Some also argue that this ratio is more suitable for assessing asset-based companies, such as manufacturing companies, rather than service-based companies, such as banking companies.

There are several studies that have been conducted regarding BVS in banking, which covers various aspects such as its use in assessing bank financial performance, its relationship with bank stock performance, and factors that influence the value of BVS in banking companies. First, the BVS ratio can be used as a good indicator to assess a bank's financial performance. In this research, it was found that the BVS ratio had a positive and significant relationship with bank financial performance, including ROA (Return on Assets) and ROE (Return on Equity). Second, the BVS ratio has a significant positive relationship with bank stock performance. In this research, it was found that the higher the BVS ratio of a bank, the higher its stock performance. Third, the BVS ratio has limitations in assessing bank financial performance, especially because this ratio does not consider factors such as asset quality, management performance and growth prospects. Fourth, factors such as bank size, ownership structure, and level of non-performing loans

can influence the BVS value of banking companies. The results of this study indicate that analysts and investors should consider these factors in assessing the BVS value and performance of banking companies. In order to overcome the limitations of using the BVS ratio, several studies have also tried to develop a more holistic assessment model by considering other factors that influence banking company performance, such as asset quality, management performance and credit risk (Kurnia & Sunarto, 2016). Overall, the development of research on BVS in banking continues to develop and is still a controversial topic. However, this research can provide useful insights for investors and analysts in assessing the intrinsic value of a bank and its financial performance.

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of BVS on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study literature development maps in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review topic research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the influence of BVS. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research BVS. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can identify research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Book Value per Share (BVS) is a measure of a company's financial performance that shows the value of equity per share issued. In the banking context, BVS is used to measure the net value or equity per share owned by a bank. This value is calculated by dividing the bank's total book value (total assets minus total liabilities) by the number of shares issued. BVS is an important indicator in fundamental analysis of banking companies. A high BVS value indicates that the bank has quite large assets and can repay its debt, thus providing a sense of security for investors. On the other hand, a low BVS value can indicate that the bank has a higher risk or there are problems in financial management.

Bibliometric studies are an analytical method used to quantitatively measure the performance of scientific publications and study patterns and trends in scientific literature. This study is conducted using bibliographic data, such as number of publications, citations, and relative success index, to identify and analyze publication and citation patterns within a particular research field or scientific discipline. In bibliometric studies, analysis is carried out using special software, such as VOSviewer, Scopus, or Web of Science, to retrieve bibliographic data from existing scientific literature databases. After the data is obtained, data processing and analysis is carried out using statistical methods and visualization techniques, such as graphs and networks. Bibliometric studies can be used for a variety of purposes, such as measuring the productivity of researchers and institutions, identifying trends and patterns in specific research fields, and assisting in decision making in research and development. This study can also help researchers to gain deeper insight into existing scientific publications and find opportunities for further research.

VOSviewer is software used in bibliometric analysis and network visualization. This software allows users to analyze the structure of scientific publications based on keywords, authors, affiliations, or subjects, and generates network-based visualizations of the analysis results. VOSviewer is used to understand relationships between concepts or topics in scientific literature, and helps users to discover trends and patterns in specific research areas. This software is very popular among scientists and researchers for visualizing and analyzing complex bibliometric data,

such as citation networks, collaboration networks, and subject networks. In VOSviewer studies, users can select various metrics relevant for bibliometric analysis, such as citation frequency, co-citations, and keyword density index, and generate attractive and easy-to-understand network visualizations. The analysis produced by VOSviewer can help users to make better decisions in their research field and identify new trends emerging in the scientific literature.

Studies Library Research is research method carried out by collecting, reviewing, and analyzing sources of information that are relevant and related to a particular topic. The purpose of a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research is to gain a deeper understanding of a particular topic, identify gaps in existing research, and formulate more focused research questions. In practice, Library Research studies involve searching and selecting relevant sources of information, such as scientific journals, books, research reports, and other documents related to the topic under study. Then, the researcher carries out an analysis of these sources to identify the findings and patterns that emerge, and connect them to the broader research context. Library Research studies can be conducted as independent research, or as part of a larger study. This method is usually used in qualitative research, but can also be used in quantitative research to identify relevant variables and formulate more focused hypotheses.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Book Value per Share (BVS). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about BVS in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Sinta via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish / Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Book Value per Share " and " BVS" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (2) mapping topics research based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

Bibliometric Study of Book Value per Share (BVS) in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 21 journal publications based on the results of data collection originating from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 2009 to 2022.

Table 1. Journal publication data about BVS by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	1	2016	2	2020	6

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Effect of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 3 influences of BVS on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

First, share price volatility. BVS is the net asset value of a company divided by the number of shares outstanding. BVS provides an overview of a company's intrinsic value and can be used as a tool to measure the fair value of a share. The influence of BVS on share price volatility in banking can vary depending on market conditions and other factors that influence share price movements. However, in general, the higher a company's BVS, the more stable its share price. This is because companies with high BVS are considered healthier and more financially stable, so investors tend to be more confident and engage in less excessive buying and selling of shares. On the other hand, companies with low BVS tend to be more susceptible to market fluctuations and share price volatility. This happens because investors tend to be more concerned about the company's ability to pay its debts and meet its financial obligations.

Second, company value. The influence of BVS on company value in banking can vary depending on market conditions and other factors that influence company valuation. However, in general, the higher the BVS of a company, the greater the company value. In banking, BVS can be used as an indicator to assess a company's ability to generate profits and obtain income from the assets it owns. A high BVS shows that the company has assets of high value and is able to manage these assets well. This can generate investor confidence and increase company valuation.

Third, stock returns. The influence of BVS on stock returns in banking can vary depending on certain factors such as market conditions, company performance and overall economic conditions. However, in general, the higher the BVS of a company, the more likely investors will get a good return from the stock. This is because BVS reflects the value of the company's assets and the company's ability to generate profits. When a company's book value increases, it means the company has more reliable assets and greater profit potential. Therefore, investors may be more inclined to buy the stock and increase demand for the stock. High demand will in turn increase share prices and provide higher returns for investors.

Fourth, intrinsic value. Most analysts agree that the BVS ratio can provide a useful indication of a bank's intrinsic value and its financial performance. By using the BVS ratio, investors can compare different banks in the same industry and determine which bank has higher intrinsic value and better financial performance. In addition, the BVS ratio can also help investors assess a company's growth prospects, especially if the company has aggressive expansion plans. If a company's BVS ratio increases over time, this indicates that the company can generate greater added value for its shareholders in the future. Ultimately, the decision to use the BVS ratio or not depends on the investor's or analyst's goals. However, most analysts agree that the BVS ratio can provide a useful indication of a bank's intrinsic value and its financial performance. Therefore, the use of the BVS ratio in the banking industry is expected to continue to grow in the future. However, investors and analysts must always take a holistic approach in assessing company performance and not rely solely on one financial ratio to determine investment decisions.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: First, the number of scientific journal publications regarding Book Value per Share (BVS) is 21 publications. And based on the visualization results using the VOS viewer

bibliometric study displays that research around influence BVS in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions is divided into 7 clusters and 74 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 24 topics, cluster 2 consists of 23 topics, cluster 3 consists of 14 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 13 topics. Second, based on a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are four main research themes regarding the influence of BVS on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Stock price volatility; (2) Company value; (3) Stock returns; and (4) Intrinsic value.

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